

VAPOR–SOLID GROWTH OF InP AND Ga₂O₃ BASED COMPOSITE NANOWIRES

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Abstract: At 400 °C, core-shell nanowires made of InP and Ga₂O₃ were produced on a Si substrate using a hydrazine (N₂H₄) vapour solution that was 3 mol.% H₂O diluted. Nanowires were grown using crystalline InP and solid Ga as source materials. The TEM and EDX results showed that the nanowires had an amorphous Ga₂O₃ outer layer and an InP core with a wurtzite-type structure. In terms of size, NWs ranged from a minimum of 14 nm in diameter to a maximum of several micrometres in length. In WZ InP cores, the twinned planes first emerged when nanowire diameters grew. The following process was postulated for the formation of core-shell nanowires based on the data collected and potential chemical reactions: the pyrolytic breakdown of hydrazine resulted in the vaporisation of intermediate NH₂, NH, and H species. In addition to dissociating into In and phosphorus precursors, the

crystalline InP source occurred at high temperatures. The volatile In₂O and Ga₂O were produced at source temperatures about 600 °C as a result of the interaction between In and Ga sources, water molecules, and byproducts of hydrazine breakdown. The Si substrate, which had been heated to 400 °C, was reached by these molecules. In the end, phosphorus precursors, Ga₂O₃, and In₂O₃ were engaged in the chemical process. The segregation of the InP and Ga₂O₃ phases was caused by an unanticipated chemical reaction. As a result of the inadequate growing temperature for Ga₂O₃ crystallisation, it formed the amorphous shell, whereas In P crystallised as a core.

Keywords: core-shell nanowire, indium phosphide, gallium (III) oxide.

Introduction

Many believe that core-shell nanostructures will be the basis for very sophisticated nanodevices in the future.¹⁻³ Processes in the shell material and core-shell interface, in addition to quantum confinement and surface dominated characteristics, are responsible for the distinctive properties of core-shell nanostructures. Without changing the size of the core nanoparticle, the emission profile and band gap of the core semiconductor may be fine-tuned by choosing the right composition and thickness of the shell material.⁴⁻⁷ In The most recent proof of concept for biofunctionalized InP/ZnS core-shell nanocrystals has sparked curiosity about their potential as a biomedical nanoprobe alternative to the very hazardous cadmium-based nanostructure.^{5, 8, 9} 1D core-shell nanostructures (nanowires, nanotubes, nanorods, nanobelts, etc.) have garnered a lot of attention and show potential for a variety of uses, much like zero-dimensional (0D) core-shell nanocrystals. Recently, a variety of core-shell nanowires (NWs) were used to create ultrasensitive dangerous gas sensors.¹⁰⁻¹³ A number of other applications of 1D nanostructures have been fruitful, including LEDs, solid quantum bits, nanowire lasers, efficient solar energy conversion, etc.

a substitute for conventional biomarkers based on cadmium, although it is quite vulnerable to oxidation. Coating InP cores with more stable shell materials greatly enhances their photostability and resistance to oxidation [5, 20], which is why scientists are becoming more

interested in developing novel InP-based core-shell nanostructures.

The goal of this project was to provide a simple method for growing core-shell nanowires based on indium phosphide.

Experimental

The nanowires were cultivated in a vertical quartz tub that was cleared of air before being filled to its saturation pressure with hydrazine (N₂H₄) vapour, which was around 10 Torr. The source for creating volatile species was a piece of flat crystalline InP coated with coarsely powdered metallic Ga. A solution of hydrazine vapour containing 3% water molecules was used to anneal the source, which was positioned near the reactor's base. The total mass of InP and Ga was between 0.50 and 0.55 g, with a weight ratio of 2.5. Volatile chemicals were produced at the surfaces of Ga and InP sources when hydrazine breakdown products were present. Sublimation then led to the formation of 1D nanomaterials on a Si substrate that was positioned 2 cm above the source.

The Si substrate temperature (growth temperature) was in the range of 400 – 430 °C, which corresponded to the source temperature of 600 – 635 °C. The nanowire growth time of was 45 – 60 min. The details of the growth technology are presented elsewhere.²¹

We used an FEI Quanta FEG 600 scanning electron microscope (SEM) to examine the structure and morphology of NWs. The pictures were captured using a transmission electron microscope (TEM) from FEI Tecnai F30 (FEG) that was outfitted with an energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) and a high-angle annular dark-field (HAADF) detector. The microscope was operated at 100 keV and had a W cathode.

Free Gibbs energies for the chemical reactions were evaluated using the computer software HSC Chemistry–6 and chemical database stored in this program.

Results and discussion

Atomic movement between the solid InP and Ga source material in the reactor's hot zone ($T_{\max} = 635$ °C) and the Si substrate 2 cm above the source (cold zone, $T_{\max} = 430$ °C) formed the foundation of the entire development process. Isolated from the vacuum system, the vertical quartz reactor operated at a static pressure of 10 Torr with N₂H₄ and 3% H₂O vapour. Nanowire development took place in this reactor. Without carrier gases, the only molecules that could reach the surface of the substrate would be those that were vaporised and volatile. Additionally, the convective flow that developed as a result of the temperature gradient between the source and the substrate facilitated the transfer of volatile species.

When hydrazine is subjected to a pyrolytic reaction with 3 moles of water, it breaks down into many very reactive pieces. Refer to references 22 and 23 for a comprehensive analysis of the thermal degradation of ammonia and hydrazine. There are typically two ways to break down hydrazine: thermal breakdown and catalytic decomposition. The former may be carried out on surfaces like semiconductors or metals, or even heated quartz reactor walls.^{24, 25} Decomposition proceeded via the formation of the following active intermediate species: NH₂, NH, N, and H. Eventually, the final stable products (N₂, H₂) were achieved. In addition, the source surface may undergo two NH₂ radical species production during the dissociative adsorption of hydrazine. Our prior work on growing single crystalline Ge₃N₄ 1D nanowires at 500 °C using volatile GeO molecules as germanium precursors was successful in confirming the significant nitriding capacity and activity of hydrazine breakdown products.²⁶ The temperature during this growth method was 350 °C lower than when the identical GeO source molecules and ammonia vapour were used to synthesise Ge₃N₄ nanowires.^{27, 28} We infer that the presence of atomic nitrogen, together with the high concentration of active NH₂ and/or NH species, is the only plausible explanation for the drastically reduced nitriding temperature in hydrazine vapour. While there were oxidising water molecules present in the hydrazine vapour (3% H₂O), the single crystalline, pure germanium nitride NWs and micrometre sized crystalline blocks were still formed.²⁶ In addition, the condensed material did not include any GeO or GeO₂, and it produced chain-like pure germanium nanostructures on the substrate.²¹ The results demonstrate that

vapour of hydrazine. Many studies on the room-temperature reduction of graphene layers from their oxides using hydrazine have verified the strong activity of hydrazine on the nanoscale range (for example, see Ref.29).

In order to create gaseous phosphorus ambient and In precursors, the InP source was thermally decomposed in the reactor. A dramatic reduction in the InP dissociation temperature was observed in the presence of hydrogen (Ref.30, 31). As an example, consider the dissociation reaction activation energy.

reduces from 154.5 kJ mol⁻¹ to 38.9 kJ mol⁻¹, and in the presence of atomic hydrogen with a concentration of 10¹⁵ cm⁻³, InP dissociates at 297 °C. The total number of N₂H₄ molecules in our 1.5 L reactor operating at 10 Torr is 4.8·10¹⁷ cm⁻³. Hydrazine at this concentration may be used to create molecular or atomic hydrogen, which is comparable to the concentrations given in references 30 and 31. Our results showing a drop in the InP dissociation temperature are consistent with this, suggesting that the observed trend is physically plausible. The presence of phosphine (PH₃) in the gaseous phase with P₄ was also observed in Ref.,30, 31, and the pressure of diphosphorus (P₂) rose to 10⁵ Torr. At the surface of the InP source, In islands with sizes of several micrometres emerged as a consequence of dissociation. The InP surface and metallic Ga, in the form of droplets, were used as NW growth sources in our experiment.

The creation of volatile molecules is necessary for the transit of Ga and In to the surface of the Si substrate. Both elements were detected in NWs grown on Si substrate situated 2 cm above the sources, as will be shown subsequently. Below, we shall propose several chemical processes that may have brought these elements to the Si substrate and produced volatile suboxides. Only inorganic and glycerol suboxides (Ga₂O and In₂O, respectively) are volatile enough to carry out this function. The only known sources for oxide production are water molecules diluted with hydrazine and a little amount of leftover oxygen in the reactor. The Gibbs free energy of formation analysis led to the conclusion that metal oxidation to Ga₂O₃ and In₂O₃ was the first step in the creation of suboxides. Then, the products of hydrazine breakdown (NH₂, NH, H) were used to reduce these compounds to suboxides. Gibbs free energy is negative for all of these reactions. Although the chemical reactions involving the Ga source are detailed here, a same pattern was found when investigating the In source's interactions with the same chemicals. Because our trials began with a pressure of 10 Torr, the following equations are provisional as they were computed for 600 °C and atmospheric pressure. Our source's temperature was 600 °C, therefore that's what we used as the reaction temperature. The first stage involves oxidising In and Ga:

Next step is the formation of volatile suboxides:

The sole thing that decides whether a chemical reaction will happen is the sign of ΔG . These reactions could happen on their own accord, as shown by the negative values of ΔG in the aforementioned equations. On the other hand, reaction kinetics—the speeds of chemical processes—determine the actual quantity of synthesised material. Volatile molecules of Ga₂O and In₂O were generated as a consequence of these reactions. Upon reaching a temperature of 400 °C on the Si substrate, they reacted with surrounding gases (P₂, P₄, PH₃, H₂O, and O₂) to produce nanowires.

Figure 1. SEM image of nanowires grown on the Si substrate.

Figure 2. High resolution TEM image of InP/Ga₂O₃ nanowire with the average diameter of 28 nm (core – 14.9 nm). The Fast Fourier Transform (inset) confirms the WZ-type structure of the core.

On the Si substrate, nanowires have developed, as seen in Figure 1, which is a SEM picture. Their length may reach tens of micrometres in certain cases. Results are shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3 from the TEM study of the nanowires' detailed structure. A crystalline core and an amorphous shell make up nanowires, as is evident. Later on, we shall think about the examination of the shell's composition. Note that no nanowire with a homogenous composition was identified on the surface of the Si substrate; instead, all nanowires exhibited a heterogeneous core-shell structure. Furthermore, the absence of catalyst tips suggests that the growth occurred via the vapor-solid method, with crystalline InP serving as the nucleation site.

Figure 3. TEM image of ZB InP/amorphous Ga₂O₃ shell nanowire with the average diameter of 37.3 nm (core – 15.7 nm). Inset shows the ZB structure of nanowire that grows along [111] direction.

Nanowires with crystalline InP cores and wurtzite (WZ) structures were determined by TEM analysis. In Figure 2's inset, you can see the Fast Fourier Transform, which clearly exhibits a wurtzite pattern. Wurtzite phases are the most common crystallisation mode for NWs, in contrast to the zincblende (ZB) type often seen in bulk non-nitride III-V materials. This behaviour has been suggested to have many theoretical grounds. The WZ phase seems to be energetically advantageous for short NW radii, according to recent simulations.³² The proportional contribution of the surfaces of the nanowire sidewalls to the total free energy increases as the radius decreases. The creation of the WZ structure is also significantly impacted by the surface dangling bonds at the lateral facets of the nanowires. The development of the wurtzite phase is thermodynamically advantageous because, as shown in Ref.³³, it reduces the sidewall surface energy by around 25%. Figure 3 shows that several core/shell nanowires were discovered, and despite their tiny diameters, they managed to retain the ZB structure. Nobody knows what's causing this phenomena just yet. Compared to ZB InP, the number of dangling bonds along the side walls of WZ structured InP is much smaller. Because a low density of interface bonds will not appreciably modify the side wall alignment, this would lead a less strained transition layer to develop between WZ InP and the amorphous, unordered gallium oxide.

The crisp interface between WZ InP and amorphous Ga₂O₃

may be shown by examining the InP side walls in Figures 2 and 3, in contrast to the rough and blurring ZB InP/Ga₂O₃ Figure 5c because to the fact that the concentrated excitation contact, which may be subject to greater stresses. electron beam was

The predominant stacking fault for III-V nanowires, which tend to develop in the [111]_B direction, are twin planes. Due to the comparatively modest twin-plane energy (about 10 mJ m⁻² for InP), twin planes that are randomly positioned spontaneously develop.³⁴ At the usual growth temperatures and reasonably high supersaturation, this energy barrier is readily overcome. The occurrence of twinning between wurtzite and zinc-blende phases becomes common for nanowires with a diameter above about 40 nanometers.³⁵ In our nanowires, we found the same thing. Figure 4 shows that TEM images showed that the twin density for NWs with bigger diameters increased gradually. Figure 4 shows a transmission electron micrograph of NW with a diameter of 74 nm, which clearly displays the high density of rotating twins. Figure 2's high resolution TEM picture also clearly detects some uncommon twins, which is an intriguing observation.

Figure 4. TEM image of InP/Ga₂O₃ core-shell nanowire with rotational twins. The diameter of nanowire was 74 nm.

Figure 5. HAADF STEM image of the nanowire (a) and EDX spectra of rectangular regions marked in (a) (b – d).

Using the EDX approach, the shell's composition was analysed. The HAADF STEM picture of NW together with three EDX spectra are shown in Figure 5. Figure 5b and 5d show that two of them came from the 1 and 3 rectangle shell

sending out the NW, starting the core and its two surrounding shells to emit X-rays at the same time. Core In and P peaks are higher than shell Ga and O peaks, as is clearly seen. It was determined that the gallium(III) oxide is the shell material by comparing these findings with the EDX spectrum of pure Ga₂O₃ powder. The spectra show a peak for copper, which is attributed to the copper TEM grid.

It is important to note that the gallium oxide shell has an amorphous structure due to its production at 400 °C when thinking about the potential processes of core-shell nanowire creation. Based on what we know, the lowest temperature for growing crystalline Ga₂O₃ (β modification) using Ga₂O precursors is 610 °C, which is too high for crystallisation to occur at this temperature.³⁶ The transmission electron micrographs (TEM) shown in Figures 2–4 show that the Ga₂O₃ shell thickness varies with the diameter of the nanowire core but is relatively constant throughout the length of the nanowire. Its growth in relation to core diameter is indicative of a unified chemical process that generated both the core and the shell at the same time.

It is hard to generate amorphous nanowires without templates, such as tubular pores or template nanowires, therefore if Ga₂O₃ were to have been formed independently, it would show up on the substrate as an amorphous layer. The following is an assumption about the growth process: the Ga₂O₃ shell was deposited on the side walls of the InP nanowire core. Tapered core-shell NWs would be the result of this. The assumption about the distinct deposition of the Ga₂O₃ shell was incorrect; instead, the developed nanowires' SEM and TEM pictures did not show any tapering, suggesting that the shells were created concurrently with the InP via a spontaneous chemical reaction.

Reducing the Gibbs free energy via a chemical reaction or a phase transition is what drives the spontaneous growth process.³⁷ The potential chemical processes that might result in the spontaneous creation of InP-Ga₂O₃ core-shell nanowires were examined, considering the available precursors. For the creation of core-shell NWs at T = 400 °C, we propose the following reactions:

$$\Delta G = -799 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$$

$$\Delta G = -798 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$$

$$\Delta G = -672 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$$

The composition of the core-shell nanowires seen in our research was achieved by reactions with Gibbs free energies that are suitably negative. It needs to be stressed again that these reactions are speculative due to the fact that they were calculated using normal state thermodynamic data. Nonetheless,

we believe that these equations adequately describe the primary trends of NW development seen in our study.

When the whole Si substrate was coated with a dense "mat" of nanowires, as seen in Figure 1, it follows that the chemical equations under consideration exhibit substantial reaction rates.

Conclusions

Hydrozazine vapour, diluted with 3 moles of water, was used to generate the core-shell nanowires on a Si substrate at 400 °C. Nanowires were grown using crystalline InP and solid Ga as source materials. The nanowires have an amorphous Ga₂O₃ coating around a wurtzite InP core, as shown by TEM and EDX analysis. In WZ InP cores, the twinned planes first emerged when nanowire diameters grew. The following process was postulated for the formation of core-shell nanowires based on the data collected and potential chemical reactions: the active intermediate NH₂, NH, and H species were released into the vapour during the pyrolytic breakdown of hydrazine. In addition to dissociating into In and phosphorus precursors, the crystalline InP source occurred at high temperatures. The volatile In₂O and Ga₂O were produced at source temperatures about 600 °C as a result of the interaction between In and Ga sources, water molecules, and byproducts of hydrazine breakdown. The Si substrate, which had been heated to 400 °C, was reached by these molecules. In the end, phosphorus precursors, Ga₂O₃, and In₂O₃ were engaged in the chemical process. The segregation of the InP and Ga₂O₃ phases was caused by an unanticipated chemical reaction. As a result of the inadequate growing temperature for Ga₂O₃ crystallisation, it formed the amorphous shell, whereas InP crystallised as a core.

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